

THE CREATIVE APPROACHES TO INCREASE INTEREST IN TEACHING NATURAL SCIENCES TO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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***Annotation:** This article describes in detail the use of creative approaches, practical methods, and the organization of work in the training field of the elementary school teacher to increase the interest in teaching natural sciences to elementary school students.*

***Keywords:** creative approach, natural sciences, science, practical methods.*

Introduction: The primary and main goal of today's education system is to educate and prepare creatively thinking qualified specialists and high-level thinkers. practice in natural sciences is an important factor of scientific production. Practice leads to the emergence, scientific formation and improvement of theory. The accuracy of knowledge is confirmed by the fact that information about a certain object is true. at the same time, if the circumstances are different, the reality may be different.

Literature analysis and methodology:

The reality in a given system may be completely different in another setting. Confirmation of the idea in practice is considered an important factor of truth. it is advisable to start training in practical work from primary grades. practical methods organized and directed by the teacher, aimed at the development of students' thinking, show that there is a complex interrelationship of speech, demonstration and practical work.

the application of practical methods is related to the intensive activity of receptors and effectors of pupils. Practical methods provide an opportunity to deeply understand the studied material, to develop skills and competencies. the use of practical methods is considered the activity of students, the source of knowledge. Such methods include oral and written exercises, laboratory work, school grounds, living nature corner, and extracurricular activities

Results:

It is necessary for the students to answer the question, problem, issue with its results before the beginning of the practical work. natural science classes are a type of practical methods of recognition and identification, teaching the characteristics of distinguishing common plants or their parts.

Approaching difference in comparison builds the learner's ability to identify. work on distinguishing and identifying is not carried out only in classes, the teacher also teaches students to find and collect plants, collect samples, their age, vegetative methods, soil sections, adaptations, and variability during nature excursions organized by the teachers should be selected based on their ability to learn. natural weapons are objects of nature. They make it possible for children to form concepts about the studied topics and nature. because the classroom may have a variety of houseplants and branches, leaves, flowers, fruits, and seeds unique to trees in their area to study living nature. natural science classes use plants grown in the nature corner, as well as plants brought from the herbarium and excursions. Natural objects can also be used to study animals.

Discussion:

giving students various objects, taking out pictures, photographs and matchboxes, cubes, cups, and asking them to find similarities and differences, then distribute geometric figures, which students put on a notebook sheet and draw around them with a pencil on paper. leads to the conclusion that the top view of the object after the completion of the task is called a plan. After that, the plan

of the table is drawn. If the students have difficulty with the size of the objects, it teaches that the depicted object can be conditionally reduced in size.

in programmed teaching, students' activity and independence in using educational material increases, the possibility of individualizing the teaching process appears, teaching with technical means is widely used, rational organization of teaching and student's work is achieved.

Summary:

in conclusion, it should be said that the elementary school teacher should take into account the climatic conditions, the location of the school, and agree on all issues with the biology student while organizing the work on the training ground. the experiment is a base of agricultural experiments and additional practical work of a young naturalist: the reason is that he grows plants that are studied in natural science classes.

starting from primary school, they study their country, their place, make observations on nature, go on excursions. During their studies in primary school, they collect rich concrete material and this material is placed in the local studies corner. over time, the most valuable materials of former elementary school graduates are collected in the local history corner, which is systematically used in teaching natural science.

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